

THE IMPORTANCE OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN THE BUILDING MATERIALS INDUSTRY

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Abstract. In this article, we explain why digital transformation is so important in the building materials industry and what steps companies can take to start the process.

Keywords: digitization, trend, building materials, transformation, efficiency, construction industry, technology, integration, industry, innovation.

INTRODUCTION

Digitization is spreading across many industries, from finance and pharmaceuticals to oil and gas. It is clear that the world has undergone a major digital transformation. Nevertheless, for reasons we will discuss later, the construction and heavy construction materials industry is lagging behind, and not without consequences. Research has shown that the construction industry is one of the least digitized industries in the world, with many companies still completing business deals with "handshakes and fax machines". Digital transformation in the building materials industry has great potential and can bring many benefits to companies such as improved efficiency and communication, higher accuracy, safer operations and lower costs. In this article, we explain why digital transformation is so important in the building materials and construction industry and what steps companies can take to start the process.

MAIN PART.

Digital transformation what and this what for important? Digital transformation is the application of digital technologies to fundamentally impact all

aspects of business and society. Many in the fields digital the transformation has been evident since the technological explosion of the 1990s. This intense changes during of companies this digital to changes adaptation or wear out danger increased went. This technological of achievements companies that have used it have certainly seen higher productivity, increased efficiency and higher profits. So what? for construction materials industry is similar way adapt didn't get it? A lot years during construction companies, unlike companies in other industries, have been able to succeed by relying on paper-based processes and communications. However, this preferential period quickly ends. Construction in the industry chronic productivity problem there is and companies demand satisfy for enough good not working. The last statistics to messages according to the world by 2040 will invest nearly \$ 79 trillion in infrastructure projects, although the actual amount needed is \$94 trillion. This is 15 trillion dollars space partially in industry innovations and technological of achievements lack of with depends to be can. This space eliminate. To achieve this, the building materials and construction industry must eliminate inefficiencies that cause projects to take longer to complete than planned and cost significantly over budget. Achieving this for information technologies more money to spend need.

Construction materials companies their own digital transformation how start can. For now this very difficult and darkness being feeling possible although, in fact, it is far from it. Innovations inspiring, useful and this great industry enterprises for Entirely can. Come on wide spread out painful points and them how overcome need seeing Let's go.

Value from the chain waste reduce. Waste places determination of the company is the first step in digital transformation. You process customer complaints seeing exit, from employees in productivity barriers and the time in vain to spend obligations descriptive feedback shapes to submit ask for equipment and delivered to give standards seeing exit through to start can. Construction in the field companies often wasting valuable time and money just waiting. Waiting for parts, people, and

equipment may seem trivial, but when added up, you can end up with large and unnecessary annual costs. Often, this waste can be reduced by eliminating manual, paper-based processes.

Impeding collaboration and information flow obstacles no do it. Mostly left handed the right hand does not know what it is doing. If teams within the company (trade, logistics, finance, etc.) independent in its goals respectively working if and cooperation if not, it is important problems appear to be can. Strategic planning and implementing a management system breaks down these silos and aligns your business activities with your vision, improves overall communication and enables performance tracking. Companies mutually functional to responsibility have has been to leaders also mutual by having to the agreement achieve possible; for example, work release and logistics both are one to the leader report gives. Your IT systems when it comes to, make sure they are up-to-date and don't require employees to enter duplicate information from one platform to another. This is one how many functional groups and operations according to leading to fragmented and incomplete data. Lack of system integration prevents companies from effectively evaluating and optimizing their processes.

Trade partners with electron connect. Internal your work in order from what you put then it's time to evaluate and improve external communication methods. This includes customers, delivery suppliers, logistics providers and external trade partners enters. Traditional electron mail is not an efficient means of electronic communication if someone later has to manually upload the data at a separate step. Using current technologies such as APIs and web services, companies are cloud-based and network-based on platforms digital integration to do enable gives, this while information in hand input efficient respectively no does. Modern contact technologies application is also spent on working with trading partners the time reduces because mobile devices and applications to users information easily observation and exchange enable gives.

Information asset recognize as. Many in companies data quality management is an undefined responsibility or assumed to be everyone's responsibility. However, before leaders can delegate this role, they must recognize data as an asset and value it like real estate, intellectual property, and equipment.

Information of quality low supply of the chain enough level not to be seen take coming, which leads to:

- of reserves lack of because of income loss;
- transport costs increase (accelerated loads);
- excess stock;
- decreased customer satisfaction.

Viewing data as an asset and putting a dollar value on poor data quality not only makes it easier to get top management buy-in for corrective action, but also helps prioritize those actions.

Look ahead. As technology evolves, construction and heavy building materials companies are approaching a crossroads: will they embrace change and begin digital transformation, or will they continue to do business as usual? Digital transformation is creating great value for the construction industry and unlocking many benefits, including:

- Improved productivity and communication;
- Safer operations;
- Less production and less error;
- Flexibility.

Conclusion:

As the number of construction objects increases from year to year, this in itself indicates the need to pay attention to the building materials and construction industry network.

Once you decide to go digital, you open yourself up to a world of innovation and ultimately higher profits. As you become more attuned to these digital changes, you'll

become better at analyzing trends and becoming more proficient in your field. Skilled activity is a picture of high-performance growth.

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